

A MICRO-MECHANICAL STUDY OF GRAPHENE REINFORCED EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the efficiency of reinforcement for pristine graphene with two different lateral size and same thicknesses within the bulk epoxy nanocomposites has been studied. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirmed both graphene have a wide size distribution and the mean lateral size of Graphene A and Graphene B are 2.67 μm and 1.37 μm , respectively. Raman spectroscopy proved these two graphene materials were both produced with low defect concentration but are poorly exfoliated. Raman four point bending tests have been carried out to study the effect of the graphene size and thickness on the graphene reinforcement efficiency. The results indicate these two types of graphene can give moderate mechanical reinforcement to an epoxy matrix.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since single-layer graphene was firstly isolated from graphite in Manchester University in 2004, it has aroused worldwide attention in material science and condensed matter physics [1]. Before its first discovery, it was thought that two-dimensional (2-D) crystal could be thermodynamically unstable at finite temperature [2]. Graphene is the 2-D crystal consists of sp^2 -hybridised carbon atoms packing into 2-D honeycomb lattice [3]. Long-range π - π conjugation in graphene gives it extraordinary electronic, mechanical and thermal properties [3].

Graphene is potentially the ideal carbon reinforcement for polymer nanocomposites as the 2-D graphene single crystal has the Young's modulus of about 1 TPa with only one atomic thick [4]. Although the interface between the pristine graphene and matrix is inferior to that of Graphene Oxide (GO), the mechanical properties of graphene are thought to be better than that of GO [5]. The mechanical properties of graphene based nanocomposites are expected to be better than those of an equivalent GO based nanocomposites. Hence, in design of the graphene based nanocomposites the balance are required to be struck between intrinsic properties of the reinforcement and the interfacial strength between polymer matrix and graphene based reinforcement.

Raman spectroscopy has been widely used to follow the stress transfer between the graphene based reinforcement and polymer matrix in nanocomposites. Gong *et al.* [6] conducted the Raman four point bending test on monolayer graphene sandwiched between SU-8 and PMMA and proved the critical length for graphene is about 3 μm . Then, they worked on graphene with different layers through similar experiment method. They found that bilayer graphene can give good reinforcement similar to that of monolayer, only when it is encapsulated well inside the polymer matrix. With the number of layers increasing, the stress transfer efficiency drops for multi-layer graphene capsulated in the polymer matrix as the interlayers between the top and bottom layers were not well strained due to the poor stress transfer between the interlayers [7].

Li *et al.* evaluated the interfacial stress transfer efficiency in wrinkled chemical vapour deposition (CVD) produced monolayer graphene on (polyethylene terephthalate) PET substrate. They found 2D band shift rate is less than 25% of that of mechanically exfoliated monolayer graphene with anomalous broadening due to the wrinkles mechanically isolating the graphene into many small islands [8]. All their work was based on single graphene flakes ideally placed on the polymer substrate with or without top coating. As in bulk graphene reinforced nanocomposite, there are many factors influencing

the mechanical reinforcement efficiency of the graphene, such as orientation of reinforced graphene, dispersion quality, folding of graphene flake and so on [9].

It is worthwhile to study the micromechanics of bulk graphene reinforced nanocomposites. This work will investigate two graphene with different lateral sizes used to fabricate epoxy-based nanocomposites. Through application of Raman spectroscopy, the Raman band shift will be monitored as a function of the strain in the matrix. The efficiency of stress transfer from matrix to graphene within the nanocomposite will then be assessed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Graphene A and Graphene B are two different grades of dry graphene powder obtained from the same Manufacturer. Details of their preparation are confidential. The epoxy resin used was a mixture of Araldite resin LY556 and hardener XB3473, supplied by Robnor Resins Limited, UK. The mixing ratio was 100:23 in weight of LY556 and XB3473. Acetone was a commercial grade and used as received.

2.2 Preparation of the epoxy-based nanocomposites

In this work, solution compounding was used to prepare the epoxy-based graphene nanocomposites. The commercial graphene were used to reinforce the epoxy matrix to fabricate nanocomposites with 0.5 w.t. %. The graphene powder was first dispersed in the acetone, followed by magnetic stirring for 2 hrs to avoid the agglomeration of graphene before addition of epoxy. The epoxy resin was then added in, followed by 2hrs magnetic stirring at room temperature to achieve a homogeneous dispersion. Then, the temperature was increased to about 80 °C to allow the evaporation of the acetone for overnight. This was followed by 2 hrs in a vacuum chamber at 80 °C to further remove the residual solvent during which the weight of the mixture was weighed every 30 mins until the weight become constant. After that, hardener was slowly added with agitation at 80 °C until the ratio of epoxy/hardener reached 100:23 and the mixture was then stirred for 10 mins to achieve a homogeneous dispersion of hardeners within the epoxy. The mixture was then placed into a vacuum chamber at 80 °C to degas for 30 mins. Then, the mixture was carefully drop-casted onto an epoxy beam (Figure 1) and cured at 140 °C for 10 hrs. During addition of hardener and degassing, the temperature was held at 80 °C to reduce the viscosity of the mixture, in order to allow good dispersion of hardeners and complete removal of bubbles inside the mixture.

2.3 Characterisation

A Philips XL30 FEG scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to characterize the samples. The SEM samples were prepared by drop-casting a solution (0.01mg/ml in DMF) onto silicon substrate, followed by drying under vacuum at 120 °C for overnight.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of graphene nanocomposite drop-casted on the epoxy beam undergoing Raman four point bending test.

A Renishaw 1000 Raman microprobe system with a He-Ne laser of wavelength at 633 nm with 10% power was used for all the Raman graphene characterization measurements. The Raman spectra for each graphene powder were collected from 20 random measurements. Raman band shifts were acquired with the four-point bending tests with the incident laser polarised parallel to the strain axis (Figure 1). The objective lens used was 50 \times and the laser spot size focused on the sample was 2 μm . The resolution of Raman scanning was 1 cm^{-1} . All the spectra were curve-fitted using Lorentzian function. The 2D bands were all forced to fit with one Lorentzian peak to determine their exact positions.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterisation of basic materials

Figure 2: (a-b) and (c-d) are SEM images for Graphene A and Graphene B, respectively.

Figure 2 shows the SEM images for graphene A and graphene B materials. It can be observed that the edges of both graphene flakes are still very straight and not very rough. This indicates these materials were not seriously damaged during the production. It also can be seen that the agglomerations of the graphene flakes are still a problem in SEM sample preparations due to the absence of the functional groups on the basal plane of pristine graphene [10]. In a polymer matrix, this absence of functional groups causes dispersion quality of graphene to be inferior to that of GO in the same polymer matrix.

As for the mechanical reinforcement, the critical length for the graphene is about 3 μm [6], it is necessary and essential to know the size distribution in order to know the potential of these materials used to do the mechanical reinforcement. Through randomly measuring the lateral size of over 200 different graphene flakes for these two materials by SEM, the size distribution of each material is created in Figure 3.

Figure 3: (a) and (b) are size distribution created by randomly measuring over 200 flakes by SEM for Graphene A and Graphene B.

Materials	Mean (μm)	Standard deviation <i>SD</i> (μm)	Median (μm)	% > 3 μm
Graphene A	2.63	± 3.13	1.88	27%
Graphene B	1.37	± 1.10	1.03	9%

Table 1: Mean, Standard deviation (*SD*), median and percentage of flakes with size larger than 3 μm for graphene A and graphene B.

Table 1 shows that the mean sizes of the graphene flakes for Graphene A and Graphene B are around 2.63 μm and 1.37 μm, respectively. About 27% of flakes of graphene A material have the flake sizes more than 3 μm with few large flakes with lateral size of tens of microns and about 9% of the graphene B materials have the lateral flake sizes larger than 3 μm with the maximum size reaching 6.2

μm . It suggests that these two kinds of graphene materials have the potential to undergo size selection [11] to help separate the large flakes with lateral size more than $3 \mu\text{m}$ in order to provide the reinforcements. However, it is not expected that these materials could give good reinforcement even after size selection, since for achieving good reinforcement the sizes are required to be more than $30 \mu\text{m}$ [6].

Figure 4: The three typical Raman spectra for Graphene A and Graphene B materials, respectively.

Materials	Band position(cm^{-1})			N	I_D/I_G	I_{2D}/I_G	$I_D/I_{D'}$
	D	G	2D				
Graphene A	1333 ± 2	1581 ± 1	2682 ± 5	Few and graphite	0.08 ± 0.05	0.44 ± 0.02	5.82 ± 3.10
Graphene B	1335 ± 1	1582 ± 1	2681 ± 6	Few and graphite	0.09 ± 0.06	0.43 ± 0.02	4.47 ± 1.88

Table 2: This table shows the parameters of D band, G band, 2D band (forced to fit with one Lorentzian peak) after fitting. N is the number of layers estimated from the 2D band positions. I_D , I_G and $I_{D'}$ and I_{2D} are the intensity for D band, G band, D' band and 2D band, respectively. All the values in this table were obtained from 20 Random Raman measurements with 633 nm laser.

The Raman spectroscopic measurements for these two materials were randomly conducted on 20 different areas of the sample powders. Three typical Raman spectra were shown in Figure 4. All the Raman spectra were scaled to have the same G band intensity for easy comparison. These Raman spectra all show the typical D band at $\sim 1331 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, G band at $\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, D' band at $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 2D band at around $\sim 2681 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

As for these two materials, the D' band can be identified beside the G band rather than being merged with it, this means all the materials have a low defects concentration. Using intensity ratio of the D band to D' band, $I_D/I_{D'}$, to identify the types of the defects through application of the theory that $I_D/I_{D'}$ for edge defects, vacancy-like defects and sp^3 defects are 3-4.5, 7 and 13, respectively [12], $I_D/I_{D'}$ of these two materials changes from 3 to 8.9 (Table 2). This indicates both materials contain edge and basal defects. The defect concentration can be quantitatively monitored by the intensity ratio of D band to G band, I_D/I_G [13]. Both materials show very low I_D/I_G between 0.03 and 0.15 (Table 2). This means that those two materials both have very low defect concentration.

In Figure 4, the 2D band of Graphene A-2 is similar to graphene with 2 or 3 layers but the band position of this peak is at 2675 cm^{-1} similar to few layer graphene [14]. The shapes of 2D band of the Graphene A-3 and Graphene B-3 appear similar to the 2D band for graphite. Apart from these peaks,

the other 2D bands in Figure 4 are similar to those of few layer graphene [15]. As the 2D band blue shifts with an increasing number of graphene layers and the relationship between the number of layers and 2D band positions has been established by Gong [14], it is possible to estimate the number of graphene layers just via the 2D band positions. Based on this, the number of graphene layers was estimated roughly and the values are shown in Table 2. It is predicted that the Graphene A and Graphene B materials contain a mixture of few-layer graphene and even graphite (flakes with more than 10 graphene layers). When using two sub-bands to do the fitting for the 2D band, $2D_1$ is on the left and $2D_2$ is on the right. In Figure 4, the 2D band of Graphene A-3 and Graphene B-3 shows a lowest shoulder of sub-band, $2D_1$. As the $2D_1$ shoulder become lower the number of layers of graphene increases. It can be predicted that Graphene A-3 and Graphene B-3 are graphite [15]. This prediction is consistent with the previous results predicted through the 2D band position. It can be concluded that Graphene A and Graphene B materials have flakes with a relatively high number of layers and even still contain some graphite, which indicates that they were poorly-exfoliated during manufacture.

3.2 Characterisation of nanocomposite

Figure 5: The Raman spectra of pure epoxy LY556, Graphene A and Graphene A reinforced epoxy nanocomposites.

Figure 5 shows typical Raman spectra for the pure epoxy LY556, Graphene A and a Graphene A reinforced epoxy nanocomposite. The identifiable 2D band in the spectrum of nanocomposite allows the 2D band to be monitored during the application of the uniaxial stress to the nanocomposite in the Raman four point bending tests.

In situ Raman measurements were performed during applying the uniaxial tensile strain to follow the deformation behavior of the nanocomposites. The nanocomposites were deformed with maximum strain up to 1%. As the 2D band is very sensitive to the strain and it shows a significant down shifting during tensile loading [6, 7], the stress induced 2D band shift was monitored during application of uniaxial strain in this work. For 0.5 w.t. % sample of Graphene A and Graphene B materials, three in situ Raman measurements were undertaken at same time on three different areas during application of strain.

Figure 6: a) and c) Graphene 2D band Raman spectra of Graphene A and Graphene B reinforced epoxy nanocomposites with 0.5 w.t. % with no strain and after applying the maximum strain, respectively. b) and d) The corresponding plots of 2D band position as a function of applied strain.

In Figure 6, through performing three in situ Raman measurements, the variations of 2D band shift with the applied tensile strain were obtained. A maximum shift rate of $-7.48 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ and $-5.85 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ were obtained for the 0.5 w.t. % Graphene A and Graphene B epoxy nanocomposites, respectively. Figure 6 a) and c) are the Raman spectra of 2D band before applying strain and after final applied strain for 0.5 w.t. % nanocomposites, respectively. Figure 6 b) and d) are plot of 2D band positions as a function of applied strain and the linear fitting lines. It is worth mentioning that some small band shift of about $-3 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ and no band shift were also obtained. This may be arising from the flakes with small lateral sizes. Here only the maximum 2D band shifts for both Graphene A and Graphene B materials are shown. No obvious changes in full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 2D band were observed during loading process. In Figure 6 b) and d), as the linear relationship is maintained to the final applied strain in both cases, which suggests the interfaces are still intact [6, 16].

It is also worth mentioning that each graphene layer can absorb 2.3% light [17]. This means the Raman laser only can penetrate the finite outer layers of a multi-layer flake [7]. It has been widely accepted that for graphitic materials the 2D band shift rate with strain is proportional to the effective Young's modulus. Since both maximum 2D band shifts are much lower than that of monolayer graphene of about $-60 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ [6, 7], this means that both measured Graphene A and Graphene B materials were not strained well in the nanocomposites. As these two materials have the very low defect concentration and the measurement was not undertaken on agglomerations, this large difference in band shift rate maybe is due to the misalignment of the measured flakes relative to the strain axis [9], wrinkles in the graphene flakes [8], weak bonding between outer graphene layers and matrix and poor stress transfer between outer graphene layers and inner graphene layers, and between each inner graphene layer through shear [18].

In applying the universal dependence of band shift upon stress for 2D band in graphitic carbon materials of $-5 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{GPa}$ [19], the effective Young's modulus for measured Graphene A and Graphene B are 150 GPa and 117 GPa. This means that only 15% and 12% of the graphene Young's modulus

has been translated to the nanocomposites, respectively [4]. The reasons for these low values are probably due to incomplete exfoliation of the graphene leading to a relatively large number of layers in the flakes, poor interfacial stress transfer and random orientation of the flakes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- Through randomly measuring over 200 flakes for each graphene material by SEM, the mean sizes of the graphene flakes for Graphene A and Graphene B were found to be mainly around 2.63 μm and 1.37 μm , respectively. Graphene A and Graphene B contain 27% and 9% flakes larger than 3 μm , respectively.
- Raman spectroscopic measurements prove that both materials had relatively low defect concentrations, but they were poorly exfoliated.
- The in situ Raman measurements under uniaxial tensile strain showed that the relatively small 2D band shifts found in these materials indicated that these materials can offer only moderate mechanical reinforcement to the nanocomposites.

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